

Phthalocyanine-Based 2D Conjugated Metal-Organic Framework Nanosheets for High-Performance Micro-Supercapacitors

Mingchao Wang, Huanhuan Shi, Panpan Zhang, Zhongquan Liao, Mao Wang, Haixia Zhong, Friedrich Schwotzer, Ali Shaygan Nia, Ehrenfried Zschech, Shengqiang Zhou, Stefan Kaskel, Renhao Dong,* and Xinliang Feng*

2D conjugated metal-organic frameworks (2D *c*-MOFs) are emerging as a novel class of conductive redox-active materials for electrochemical energy storage. However, developing 2D *c*-MOFs as flexible thin-film electrodes have been largely limited, due to the lack of capability of solution-processing and integration into nanodevices arising from the rigid powder samples by solvothermal synthesis. Here, the synthesis of phthalocyanine-based 2D *c*-MOF (Ni₂[CuPc(NH)₈]) nanosheets through ball milling mechanical exfoliation method are reported. The nanosheets feature with average lateral size of ≈160 nm and mean thickness of ≈7 nm (≈10 layers), and exhibit high crystallinity and chemical stability as well as a p-type semiconducting behavior with mobility of ≈1.5 cm² V⁻¹ s⁻¹ at room temperature. Benefiting from the ultrathin feature, the nanosheets allow high utilization of active sites and facile solution-processability. Thus, micro-supercapacitor (MSC) devices are fabricated mixing Ni₂[CuPc(NH)₈] nanosheets with exfoliated graphene, which display outstanding cycling stability and a high areal capacitance up to 18.9 mF cm⁻²; the performance surpasses most of the reported conducting polymers-based and 2D materials-based MSCs.

1. Introduction

2D conjugated metal-organic frameworks (2D *c*-MOFs),^[1] which represent a new generation of layer-stacked MOFs with strong in-plane conjugation and weak out-of-plane van der Waals interactions,^[2] have emerged as promising electrode materials for energy applications,^[3] owing to the intrinsic conductivity, versatile structures,^[3b] and well-defined active sites as well as tunable porosity.^[4] Particularly, 2D *c*-MOFs have been reported to exhibit high performance in supercapacitors.^[5] For instance, a Ni₃(HITP)₂ (HITP = 2,3,6,7,10,11-hexamino-triphenylene) 2D *c*-MOF with diradical nickel-bis(*o*-diiminobenzos-emiquinonate) active sites has shown a gravimetric capacitance of ≈110 F g⁻¹ and an areal capacitance of ≈18 μF cm⁻² in an electrochemical double layer (EDL) supercapacitor.^[5b] Besides the EDL charge

storage, another Ni₃(HIB)₂ (HIB = hexaminobenzene) 2D *c*-MOF has exhibited a pseudocapacitive charge storage with a volumetric capacitance up to 760 F cm⁻³.^[5c] Despite the great progress of 2D *c*-MOFs for supercapacitors, the utilization of 2D *c*-MOFs as thin-film electrodes^[6] for flexible micro-supercapacitors (MSCs)^[7]—a smaller and lighter micro-power source for next-generation portable electronic devices^[8]—has been largely impeded by the lack of capability of solution-processing and integration into nanodevices arising from the rigid particle morphology of the bulk powders by solvothermal synthesis. To address this challenge, the delamination of bulk materials into thin nanosheets is an efficient approach that can maintain the 2D nature and intrinsic conductivity.^[9] For instance, ultrasonic treatment has been demonstrated to the top-down synthesis of a 2D non-conjugated MOF (Zn₂(TPA)₄(H₂O)₂·2DMF, TPA = terephthalate, and DMF = dimethylformamide) nanosheets,^[9a] which are held together by the weak hydrogen-bonding interactions in the bulk crystals. Whereas the nanosheets allow the high utilization of active sites and facile solution-processing toward device fabrication,^[10] top-down exfoliation of van der Waal stacked 2D *c*-MOFs into thin nanosheets and the related MSC devices have remained unexplored.

M. Wang, H. Shi, Dr. P. Zhang, Dr. H. Zhong, F. Schwotzer, Dr. A. S. Nia, Prof. S. Kaskel, Dr. R. Dong, Prof. X. Feng
Center for Advancing Electronics Dresden (cfaed) & Faculty of Chemistry and Food Chemistry
Technische Universität Dresden
Mommsenstrasse 4, Dresden 01062, Germany
E-mail: renhao.dong@tu-dresden.de; xinliang.feng@tu-dresden.de
Dr. Z. Liao, Prof. E. Zschech
Fraunhofer Institute for Ceramic Technologies and Systems (IKTS)
Dresden 01109, Germany
Dr. M. Wang, Dr. S. Zhou
Institute of Ion Beam Physics and Materials Research
Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf
Dresden 01328, Germany

 The ORCID identification number(s) for the author(s) of this article can be found under <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.202002664>.

© 2020 The Authors. Published by WILEY-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA, Weinheim. This is an open access article under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

DOI: 10.1002/adfm.202002664

Herein, we report the synthesis and delamination of a novel phthalocyanine-based layer-stacked 2D *c*-MOF ($\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]$) with Ni-bis(*o*-diiminobenzosemiquinonate) redox active centres into nanosheets. The highly crystalline bulk samples with the domain size of ≈ 200 nm were prepared by solvothermal synthesis, and presented high specific surface area up to $690 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ and high chemical stability in acid/alkaline aqueous solution and other polar solvents. Subsequently, NaCl-assisted ball milling was performed for the mechanical exfoliation of the bulk crystals into nanosheets. The achieved 2D *c*-MOF nanosheets feature with average lateral size of ≈ 160 nm and mean thickness of ≈ 7 nm (corresponding to ≈ 10 layers), which can be homogeneously dispersed in DMF for more than 6 months. The conductivity of the 2D *c*-MOF nanosheets was determined as 0.01 S m^{-1} based on a van der Pauw pattern. The Hall effect measurement revealed a p-type semiconducting behavior with mobility of $\approx 1.5 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at room temperature. Benefiting from the intrinsic conductivity and porosity, high crystallinity, and ultrathin feature that allows high exposure of active sites and fast ion diffusion as well as facile film processability of the nanosheets samples, MSC devices were fabricated based on $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]$ /graphene hybrids, which exhibited outstanding cycling stability and a high areal capacitance up to 18.9 mF cm^{-2} . The achieved areal capacitance is superior to most of the reported conducting polymers and 2D materials for MSCs (Table S1, Supporting Information). Our work opens

up an avenue on the top-down scalable synthesis of conductive 2D *c*-MOF nanosheets toward energy storage applications with high performance.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Synthesis and Characterization of Bulk Crystals of $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]$

The bulk $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]$ was synthesized through the coordination reaction between 2,3,9,10,16,17,23,24-octaaminophthalocyaninato copper [II] (OAPcCu) ligand (Figure 1a) and $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) at 60°C with the existence of $\text{NH}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$. The achieved $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]$ is black powder sample comprising aggregated crystals featuring with Ni-bis(diimine) linkages, which are the known redox active centres for energy storage.^[5b,c] The powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) pattern with Cu $K\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.54 \text{ \AA}$) of the as-prepared bulk $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]$ exhibited peaks at $2\theta = 4.91^\circ, 7.01^\circ, 9.89^\circ, 14.81^\circ, 15.63^\circ, 19.80^\circ, 22.17^\circ,$ and 27.51° , assignable to (100), (110), (200), (210), (300), (310), (400), (420), and (002) lattice planes, respectively, indicative of long-range order within the ab-plane with a center-to-center (neighbouring Cu...Cu) distance of 18.0 \AA (Figure 1b, black line and Figure S1, Supporting Information). The broad peak at 27.51° —that is common in

Figure 1. Characterizations of bulk $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]$ 2D *c*-MOF. a) Schematic illustration of the MOF synthesis in DMSO. b) Experimental (black, without modification, with Cu $K\alpha$ radiation) and simulated PXRD patterns for AA-eclipsed (green), AA-serrated (red), AA-inclined (blue), and AB (magenta) stacking mode. The insets are the enlarged experimental ((200) peak is not displayed), simulated AA-eclipsed, and AA-serrated XRD patterns. c) Top and side view of simulated AA-serrated stacked multilayers (C: grey, N: blue, Cu: orange, Ni: green). d) SEM image. e) TEM image. The inset is the related FFT analysis. f) Chemical stability in different solvents by measuring the XRD.

layered 2D framework materials—suggests less coherence of the stacked $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]$ layers in the out-of-plane direction and corresponds to an interlayer distance of 3.24 Å. Additionally, we performed structural modeling with several possible interlayer arrangements (Figure 1c and Figure S2, Supporting Information) by density functional theory (DFT) method. As shown in Figure 1b, the experimental XRD pattern rules out the AA-eclipsed, AA-inclined as well as AB stacking, and can be reproduced well with AA-serrated geometry, which is energetically most favored (Table S2, Supporting Information). Therefore, the peak at 27.51° is assigned to the (002) lattice plane and $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]$ can be fully defined by square unit cells with $a = b = 18.0$ Å. Field-emission scanning electron microscopy indicated that this MOF presented stacked sheet-like morphologies, where the size of sheets was estimated as 100–300 nm (Figure 1d and Figure S3, Supporting Information). Corresponding energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) spectroscopy evidenced the uniform element distribution of C, N, Cu, and Ni (Figure S4, Supporting Information). Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) imaging showed the layer-stacked crystallites (Figure 1e and Figure S5, Supporting Information). Fast Fourier transform (FFT) analysis confirmed the (100) crystallographic plane, which agrees well with the XRD result.

Fourier-transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy revealed the disappearance of the N–H stretching vibration band from the monomer OAPcCu in the $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]$ (Figure S6, Supporting Information), which further demonstrated the successful coordination polymerization. The porosity of $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]$ was evaluated by low-pressure CO_2 adsorption at 195 K (Figure S7a, Supporting Information), which showed a type I isotherm and a BET surface area of 690 $\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$. According to the quench solid DFT, the average pore size was calculated as 0.9–1.7 nm. Analogous to CO_2 , nitrogen adsorption at 77.3 K revealed similar behavior with surface area of 659 $\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$ and pore size of 0.6–1.5 nm (Figure S7b, Supporting Information). Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) exhibited no significant weight loss at temperature up to 310 °C in argon (Figure S8, Supporting Information). To determine the chemical stability of $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]$, various organic solvents and aqueous solutions, including DMF, ethanol, water, 1 M KOH, and 1 M HCl were examined; the related XRD patterns demonstrated the integrity of its crystalline structure after immersing for 24 h at room temperature (Figure 1f). Notably, the (100) and (002) peaks were shifted from 4.91° and 27.51° to 5.58° and 27.06° after soaking in 1 M HCl, respectively, which is attributed to the protonation of imine units in MOFs.

2.2. $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]$ 2D *c*-MOF Nanosheets

Ball milling has been demonstrated as an efficient top-down synthetic strategy^[11] for preparing graphene, 2D carbon nitrides, and 2D transition metal dichalcogenides nanosheets. Using the low energy ball milling method, the well-defined bulk $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]$ crystals were mechanically exfoliated into nanosheets with 40–50% yield. During the exfoliation, the addition of NaCl as controlling agent played a key role in inserting into the layers, reducing the shear forces and mildly separating the stacked MOF layers (Figure 2a), which resulted in larger-sized

nanosheets compared with the contrast flakes obtained in the absence of NaCl. The resultant nanosheets can be homogeneously dispersed in DMF for more than 6 months after mild sonication (Figure 2b and Figure S9, Supporting Information).

Figure 2c shows the XRD pattern of the MOF nanosheets, which present intensive (100) and (002) diffraction peaks. Notably, the shift of the (002) peak from 27.51° to 26.74° correlates with an increase in the *c* parameter from 3.24 Å to 3.33 Å, indicative of swollen layers after delamination by the milling process. SEM and TEM images (Figure 2d and Figure S10, Supporting Information) reveal thin nanosheets with size distribution ranging from 50 to ≈600 nm. Based on the statistical analysis of 220 individual nanosheets, the average size was estimated to be ≈160 nm (Figure S11, Supporting Information). High resolution TEM image unambiguously confirmed the square unit cells at the molecular level with lattice parameter of $a = b = 1.7$ nm in the nanosheets (Figure 2e). Atomic force microscopy (AFM) images revealed the mean thickness of the nanosheets as ≈7 nm, corresponding to ≈10 layers of $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]$ (Figure 2f).

After exfoliation, the composition in the nanosheet samples was remained, as suggested by FT-IR spectroscopy characterizations (Figure S12, Supporting Information). The survey spectrum by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy further revealed the presence of C, N, Cu, Ni, and O elements (Figure S13, Supporting Information). Deconvolution of the N(1s) and Ni(2p) signals showed three types of N (N = C–N, N–Ni, and N–Cu) and a single type of Ni (Ni–N) atoms. No other counter ions could be detected, which reveals that $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]$ is a charge-neutral material. To investigate the charge transport property, macroscopic conductivity measurement was applied in a van der Pauw configuration on the assembled nanosheets (Figure S14, Supporting Information). Linear current–voltage (*I*–*V*) curves confirm the ohmic contact during the whole measurement (Figure S15, Supporting Information); temperature (*T*)-dependent measurement indicated a semiconducting non-linear drop of conductivity (σ) upon cooling from 310 to 100 K (Figure 2g). Based on the above data, we obtained a conductivity of ≈0.01 S m^{-1} at 300 K. As shown in the inset of Figure 2g, the plot of σ versus $T^{-1/4}$ over the measured temperature region can be well fitted to the Mott variable range hopping (Mott–VRH) model ($\sigma(T) = \sigma_0 \exp[-(T_0/T)^{1/4}]$), which describes the temperature dependence of hopping conductivity in the polycrystalline nanosheets. Hall effect measurement was applied under a magnetic field (–4 to 4 T) perpendicular to the sample plane at 300 K. $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]$ nanosheets exhibit a linear relationship of Hall resistance to the magnetic field (Figure 2h); moreover, the polarity indicates a p-type semiconducting behavior with carrier (holes) density of ≈ $6 \times 10^{14} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and mobility of $1.6 \pm 0.2 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

2.3. $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]$ -Based MSCs

Benefiting from the intrinsic conductivity and porosity, high crystallinity, and ultrathin feature that provide sufficient accessible active sites^[12] and fast ion diffusion^[13] as well as facile film processability, 2D *c*-MOF nanosheets hold great potential application in flexible energy storage devices. As a proof of concept,

Figure 2. Exfoliation of bulk $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]$ 2D *c*-MOF into nanosheets. a) Schematic illustration of the exfoliation. b) The homogeneous dispersion of $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]$ in DMF at a concentration $\approx 0.3 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$ (left). The left sample diluted by ≈ 40 times and the observed Tyndall effect are shown on the right. c) XRD pattern before (red) and after (black) exfoliation. d) TEM image. The inset is SEM image. e) HR-TEM image. f) AFM images. g) Temperature-dependent electrical conductivity. The inset is σ as a function of $T^{-1/4}$. The red line refers to the fitting for Hopping conductivity. h) Hall resistance as a function of magnetic field at 300 K.

$\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]$ nanosheets were mixed with electrochemically exfoliated graphene (EG, conductive platform, exfoliation details seen in Supporting Information) nanosheets (in different mass ratios) and filtered subsequently with a home-made mask into interdigital electrodes for flexible MSCs (Figure 3a,b and Figures S16 and S17, Supporting Information). The electrochemical behavior of MSCs based on pure EG thin film and $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]/\text{EG}-x$ (x represents the mass ratio of graphene/ $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]$) were investigated firstly by cyclic voltammetry (CV) measurement. It is clearly shown that the integral area of CV curve for $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]/\text{EG}-2$ based MSC (abbreviated as $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]/\text{EG}-2$) presents the maximum value compared with other fabricated devices (Figure 3c). Therefore, the weight ratio of graphene/ $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]$ = 2 was found to

be the optimized one for the construction of $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]/\text{EG}$ -based MSC electrode. The CV profiles of $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]/\text{EG}-2$ display the nearly rectangular shape at scan rates from 2 to 50 mV s^{-1} (Figure 3d), resulting from the high specific surface area and well-defined structure of $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]$. In addition, the capacitive behavior of $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]/\text{EG}-2$ was investigated through galvanostatic charge–discharge (GCD) measurement at various current densities of $0.04\text{--}0.4 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$ (Figure 3e).

Based on the optimized conditions, $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]/\text{EG}-2$ delivered an areal capacitance of 18.9 mF cm^{-2} at a current density of 0.04 mA cm^{-2} (Figure 4a), which is higher than those of recently reported conducting polymers-based and 2D materials-based MSCs (Table S1, Supporting Information), such

Figure 3. Electrochemical behavior of the $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]/\text{graphene}$ -based MSCs. a) Optical photographs of the fabricated interdigital pattern and corresponding $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]/\text{EG}$ -based MSCs on polyimide substrate prepared by mask-assisted vacuum filtration. b) Side-view SEM images of $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]/\text{EG}$ hybrid thin film transferred on Si wafer and the corresponding EDX elemental mapping analysis of C (red), N (yellow), Ni (orange), and Cu (magenta) elements, respectively. c) Comparison of CV curves of MSCs based on EG and $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]/\text{EG}$ with different mass ratios at 50 mV s^{-1} . d) CV curves of $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]/\text{EG-2}$ -based MSC at various scan rates of $2\text{--}50 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$. e) GCD curves of $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]/\text{EG-2}$ -based MSC at different current densities of $0.04\text{--}0.4 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$.

as benzene-bridged polypyrrole (0.35 and 0.95 mF cm^{-2}),^[14] azulene-bridged coordination polymer (0.1 mF cm^{-2}),^[15] graphene/carbon nanotube (CNT) (6.1 and 2.16 mF cm^{-2}),^[16] thiophene/graphene (3.9 mF cm^{-2}),^[17] phosphorene/graphene (9.8 mF cm^{-2}),^[18] 2D *c*-MOF/graphene (LSG/Ni-CAT MOF, 15.2 mF cm^{-2}),^[19] covalent organic framework/CNT (15.2 mF cm^{-2}),^[20] and $\text{V}_2\text{O}_5/\text{graphene}$ (3.9 mF cm^{-2}).^[21] Moreover, this device exhibited excellent cycling stability with 91.4% of capacitance retention after 5000 charge/discharge cycles (Figure 4b). The cycling stability agrees well with the absence of any morphological changes during the cycling processes. After the cycling measurements, only slight increase in the equivalent series resistance was observed (Figure S18, Supporting Information), which might be resulted from the solvent evaporation of the electrolyte. To further demonstrate the overall performance of $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]/\text{EG-2}$, Ragone plots were presented in Figure 4c. Notably, our fabricated MSCs delivered an ultrahigh areal power density of 168 mW cm^{-2} at $1.1 \mu\text{Wh cm}^{-2}$, which is comparable to those of recently reported graphene-based MSCs,^[16,19,22] conducting polymer-based MSCs,^[23] and carbon-based MSCs.^[24] In addition, $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]/\text{EG-2}$ also provided high areal energy density of $1.7 \mu\text{Wh cm}^{-2}$ at 16 mW cm^{-2} , which is superior to that of carbon-based MSCs ($0.1\text{--}1 \mu\text{Wh cm}^{-2}$).^[16,24]

On the other hand, flexibility and variable working window are crucial for portable and wearable energy storage devices. As depicted in Figure 4d,e, no obvious change of CV curves was observed at different bending angles, highlighting the excellent

mechanical flexibility and electrochemical stability of the device. Even alternating the flat and bent states, our $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]/\text{EG-2}$ based MSCs maintained 86.2% of their initial performance after 3000 cycles (Figure 4f). Moreover, different working windows and prolonged discharging time could be achieved by the series or parallel connection of as-fabricated MSCs, demonstrating the good integration capability (Figure S19, Supporting Information).

3. Conclusion

In summary, we demonstrated the efficient synthesis and delamination of phthalocyanine-based 2D *c*-MOF $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]$ into ultrathin nanosheets by top-down ball milling exfoliation. The ultrathin $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]$ nanosheets possess intrinsic conductivity, porosity and high crystallinity as well as high chemical stability. For the utilization as energy storage material, the $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]$ 2D *c*-MOF based MSC device exhibited outstanding mechanical flexibility, cycling stability, and a high areal capacitance of 18.9 mF cm^{-2} . Our work provides a guideline for the top-down exfoliation of 2D *c*-MOF nanosheets and sheds light on realizing their function in flexible MSCs. By further modifying the chemical structures with redox active sites and improving the crystallinity and porosity as well as conductivity, we highlight the great potential of 2D *c*-MOFs for developing flexible electronic devices.

Figure 4. Performance of the optimized $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]/\text{EG-2}$ -based MSC. a) Specific capacitances calculated from GCD curves as a function of current density. b) Cycling stability measured at 0.4 mA cm^{-2} under voltage window of 0.8 V . c) Ragone plots for MSCs based on $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]/\text{EG}$, conducting polymers, carbon/graphene, and other framework materials. d) Optical photographs of the $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]/\text{EG-2}$ based MSC under different bending angles. e) CV curves of the $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]/\text{EG-2}$ based MSC bended at different angles of $30^\circ, 60^\circ,$ and 90° at 10 mV s^{-1} . f) Capacitance retention in the alternative flat and bent configurations after 3000 cycles at 20 mV s^{-1} . The inset shows the photographs of the MSC in the flat and bent states.

4. Experimental Section

Synthesis of Bulk $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]$ 2D c-MOF: All chemicals were purchased from commercial suppliers and used without further purification. 2,3,9,10,16,17,23,24-octaamino-phthalocyaninato copper [II] (OAPcCu) was synthesized according to the known procedure.^[25] OAPcCu (5.00 mg) was dissolved in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO, 3 mL) and ammonia solution (50% v/v, 0.1 mL). The mixture was stirred at 60°C in a sand bath under air. Then $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (3 mg) in DMSO (1 mL) and ammonia solution (50% v/v, 0.1 mL) was added at this temperature. The reaction mixture was stirred for 30 min and stand for 8 h at 60°C . After cooling to room temperature, the obtained solids were filtered, washed with *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF), H_2O , and acetone, respectively. The solids were stirred in deionized water (20 mL) for 6 h, and water was exchanged 6 times. Bulk $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]$ 2D MOF was collected by filtration, washed with acetone, and dried under vacuum at 100°C overnight as black powder.

Synthesis of $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]$ Nanosheets: To $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]$ (0.1 g) and NaCl (1 g) in a 45 mL grinding bowl, steel balls (50 g) were added under argon. Milling was performed for 6 h at 100 rpm. After delamination, the nanosheets were washed with deionized water for 6 times and then DMF by centrifugation (5000 rpm, 5 min). The resultant material was dispersed into DMF by mild sonication for 15 min in an ice bath. After centrifugation at 2000 rpm for 10 min to remove thick-layered flakes, homogeneous $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]$ dispersion was obtained and used for characterization as well as device fabrication.

$\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]/\text{Graphene}$ Hybrid and Device Fabrication: EG dispersion ($\approx 0.3 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$) and $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]$ dispersion ($\approx 0.3 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$) in DMF were mixed with different volume ratios and sonicated for 10 min. A home-made mask with 8 interdigital fingers (width of 1 mm, length of 10 mm, and interspace of 1 mm) was covered

on the polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF, $0.2 \mu\text{m}$, 47 mm in size) membrane filter. Then, the mixture was dropped into the channels of the mask and vacuum-filtrated to obtain the hybrid film with interdigital pattern. Immediately, the resultant mid-wet pattern was directly transferred onto a flexible polyimide (PI) substrate. Afterwards, PVA/LiCl gel electrolyte (1 mL) was drop-casted onto the surface of interdigital electrode and solidified overnight. Finally, all solid-state $\text{Ni}_2[\text{CuPc}(\text{NH})_8]/\text{EG}$ -based in-plane MSCs were fabricated. For comparison, the EG film-based MSCs were prepared under the similar experimental condition without adding MOF. The PVA/LiCl gel electrolyte was prepared by mixing PVA (molecular weight 85 000-124 000, 2 g) and LiCl (4.24 g) in deionized water (20 mL), and heated at 85°C until forming a clear solution.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

Acknowledgements

M.W., H.S., and P.Z. contributed equally to this work. This work was financially supported by ERC Starting Grant (FC2DMOF, No. 852909), ERC Consolidator Grant (T2DCP), Coordination Networks: Building Blocks for Functional Systems (SPP 1928, COORNETS), European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (GrapheneCore2 785219), DFG project (2D polyanilines) and Center of Advancing Electronics Dresden, EXC1056, (cfaed). The authors thank Dr. Petko St. Petkov and Prof. Dr. Thomas Heine for the DFT calculation,

with the computational resources from the Centre for Information Services and High Performance Computing (ZIH) at TU Dresden. The authors acknowledge the Dresden Center for Nanoanalysis (DCN), Dr. Philipp Schlender, and Dr. Konrad Schneider (Leibniz Institute for Polymer Research, IPF, Dresden) for the use of facilities. The authors also appreciate Dr. Yu Zhang (UvA), Dr. Minghao Yu, Dr. Chongqing Yang, Dr. Haoyuan Qi, Mr. SangWook Park, and Mr. Zichao Li (HZDR) for helpful discussions.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Keywords

2D conjugated metal-organic frameworks, energy storage, micro-supercapacitor, milling exfoliation, ultrathin nanosheets

Received: March 24, 2020

Revised: April 18, 2020

Published online: June 11, 2020

- [1] a) T. Kambe, R. Sakamoto, K. Hoshiko, K. Takada, M. Miyachi, J.-H. Ryu, S. Sasaki, J. Kim, K. Nakazato, M. Takata, H. Nishihara, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2013**, *135*, 2462; b) X. Huang, P. Sheng, Z. Tu, F. Zhang, J. Wang, H. Geng, Y. Zou, C.-a. Di, Y. Yi, Y. Sun, W. Xu, D. Zhu, *Nat. Commun.* **2015**, *6*, 7408; c) A. J. Clough, J. M. Skelton, C. A. Downes, A. A. de la Rosa, J. W. Yoo, A. Walsh, B. C. Melot, S. C. Marinescu, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2017**, *139*, 10863; d) Z. Meng, A. Aykanat, K. A. Mirica, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2019**, *141*, 2046.
- [2] a) A. Ciesielski, P. Samori, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2014**, *43*, 381; b) A. Schneemann, V. Bon, I. Schwedler, I. Senkovska, S. Kaskel, R. A. Fischer, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2014**, *43*, 6062.
- [3] a) P. Zhang, F. Wang, M. Yu, X. Zhuang, X. Feng, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2018**, *47*, 7426; b) X. Li, X. Yang, H. Xue, H. Pang, Q. Xu, *Energy-Chem* **2020**, *2*, 100027.
- [4] a) H. Furukawa, N. Ko, Y. B. Go, N. Aratani, S. B. Choi, E. Choi, A. Ö. Yazaydin, R. Q. Snurr, M. O’Keeffe, J. Kim, O. M. Yaghi, *Science* **2010**, *329*, 424; b) Q. L. Zhu, Q. Xu, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2014**, *43*, 5468.
- [5] a) S. Bi, H. Banda, M. Chen, L. Niu, M. Chen, T. Wu, J. Wang, R. Wang, J. Feng, T. Chen, M. Dincă, A. A. Kornyshev, G. Feng, *Nat. Mater.* **2020**, *19*, 552; b) D. Sheberla, J. C. Bachman, J. S. Elias, C. J. Sun, Y. Shao-Horn, M. Dincă, *Nat. Mater.* **2017**, *16*, 220; c) D. Feng, T. Lei, M. R. Lukatskaya, J. Park, Z. Huang, M. Lee, L. Shaw, S. Chen, A. A. Yakovenko, A. Kulkarni, J. Xiao, K. Fredrickson, J. B. Tok, X. Zou, Y. Cui, Z. Bao, *Nat. Energy* **2018**, *3*, 30; d) W.-H. Li, K. Ding, H.-R. Tian, M.-S. Yao, B. Nath, W.-H. Deng, Y. Wang, G. Xu, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2017**, *27*, 1702067.
- [6] a) Y. Lin, Y. Gao, F. Fang, Z. Fan, *Nano Res.* **2018**, *11*, 3065; b) M. Ye, Z. Zhang, Y. Zhao, L. Qu, *Joule* **2018**, *2*, 245; c) M. R. Lukatskaya, O. Mashtalir, C. E. Ren, Y. Dall’Agnese, P. Rozier, P. L. Taberna, M. Naguib, P. Simon, M. W. Barsoum, Y. Gogotsi, *Science* **2013**, *341*, 1502; d) F. Bonaccorso, L. Colombo, G. Yu, M. Stoller, V. Tozzini, A. C. Ferrari, R. S. Ruoff, V. Pellegrini, *Science* **2015**, *347*, 1246501.
- [7] a) N. Liu, Y. Gao, *Small* **2017**, *13*, 1701989; b) Y. Shao, M. F. El-Kady, J. Sun, Y. Li, Q. Zhang, M. Zhu, H. Wang, B. Dunn, R. B. Kaner, *Chem. Rev.* **2018**, *118*, 9233; c) H. Li, J. Liang, *Adv. Mater.* **2020**, *32*, 1805864.
- [8] a) M. Beidaghi, Y. Gogotsi, *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2014**, *7*, 867; b) Y. Da, J. Liu, L. Zhou, X. Zhu, X. Chen, L. Fu, *Adv. Mater.* **2019**, *31*, 1802793.
- [9] a) P.-Z. Li, Y. Maeda, Q. Xu, *Chem. Commun.* **2011**, *47*, 8436; b) H. Shi, M. Li, A. S. Nia, M. Wang, S. Park, Z. Zhang, M. R. Lohe, S. Yang, X. Feng, *Adv. Mater.* **2020**, *32*, 1907244.
- [10] a) Z. Zeng, Z. Yin, X. Huang, H. Li, Q. He, G. Lu, F. Boey, H. Zhang, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **2011**, *50*, 11093; b) Z. Lin, Y. Liu, U. Halim, M. Ding, Y. Liu, Y. Wang, C. Jia, P. Chen, X. Duan, C. Wang, F. Song, M. Li, C. Wan, Y. Huang, X. Duan, *Nature* **2018**, *562*, 254.
- [11] a) I.-Y. Jeon, H.-J. Choi, S.-M. Jung, J.-M. Seo, M.-J. Kim, L. Dai, J.-B. Baek, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2013**, *135*, 1386; b) L. Dai, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2013**, *46*, 31.
- [12] a) M. Zhao, Y. Huang, Y. Peng, Z. Huang, Q. Ma, H. Zhang, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2018**, *47*, 6267; b) R. Dong, T. Zhang, X. Feng, *Chem. Rev.* **2018**, *118*, 6189.
- [13] S. Zhao, Y. Wang, J. Dong, C.-T. He, H. Yin, P. An, K. Zhao, X. Zhang, C. Gao, L. Zhang, J. Lv, J. Wang, J. Zhang, A. M. Khatkhat, N. A. Khan, Z. Wei, J. Zhang, S. Liu, H. Zhao, Z. Tang, *Nat. Energy* **2016**, *1*, 16184.
- [14] K. Jiang, I. A. Baburin, P. Han, C. Yang, X. Fu, Y. Yao, J. Li, E. Cánovas, G. Seifert, J. Chen, M. Bonn, X. Feng, X. Zhuang, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2020**, *30*, 1908243.
- [15] C. Yang, K. S. Schellhammer, F. Ortmann, S. Sun, R. Dong, M. Karakus, Z. Mics, M. Löffler, F. Zhang, X. Zhuang, E. Cánovas, G. Cuniberti, M. Bonn, X. Feng, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **2017**, *56*, 3920.
- [16] a) M. Beidaghi, C. Wang, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2012**, *22*, 4501; b) J. Lin, C. Zhang, Z. Yan, Y. Zhu, Z. Peng, R. H. Hauge, D. Natelson, J. M. Tour, *Nano Lett.* **2013**, *13*, 72.
- [17] Z.-S. Wu, Y. Zheng, S. Zheng, S. Wang, C. Sun, K. Parvez, T. Ikeda, X. Bao, K. Müllen, X. Feng, *Adv. Mater.* **2017**, *29*, 1602960.
- [18] H. Xiao, Z.-S. Wu, L. Chen, F. Zhou, S. Zheng, W. Ren, H.-M. Cheng, X. Bao, *ACS Nano* **2017**, *11*, 7284.
- [19] H. Wu, W. Zhang, S. Kandambeth, O. Shekhah, M. Eddaoudi, H. N. Alshareef, *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2019**, *9*, 1900482.
- [20] J. Xu, Y. He, S. Bi, M. Wang, P. Yang, D. Wu, J. Wang, F. Zhang, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **2019**, *58*, 12065.
- [21] P. Zhang, F. Zhu, F. Wang, J. Wang, R. Dong, X. Zhuang, O. G. Schmidt, X. Feng, *Adv. Mater.* **2017**, *29*, 1604491.
- [22] M. F. El-Kady, R. B. Kaner, *Nat. Commun.* **2013**, *4*, 1475.
- [23] C. Z. Meng, J. Maeng, S. W. M. John, P. P. Irazoqui, *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2014**, *4*, 1301269.
- [24] D. Pech, M. Brunet, H. Durou, P. Huang, V. Mochalin, Y. Gogotsi, P.-L. Taberna, P. Simon, *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **2010**, *5*, 651.
- [25] M. Wang, M. Ballabio, M. Wang, H.-H. Lin, B. P. Biswal, X. Han, S. Paasch, E. Brunner, P. Liu, M. Chen, M. Bonn, T. Heine, S. Zhou, E. Cánovas, R. Dong, X. Feng, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2019**, *141*, 16810.